

ASSESSMENT OF THE VULNERABILITY OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM BASED ON FUZZY MATHEMATICS

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ОЦІНЮВАННЯ ВРАЗЛИВОСТІ ІНФОРМАЦІЙНОЇ СИСТЕМИ НА ОСНОВІ FUZZY-МАТЕМАТИКИ

Abstract. A fuzzy-mathematics approach for assessing the vulnerability of information systems has been proposed. This approach is based on systems analysis, viewing the information system as an interaction between subjects and objects governed by access control policies. The key elements are Assessing the vulnerability of objects, Monitoring anomalies, Evaluating risk levels, and Adjusting access policies. This approach allows for dynamic responses to changes in the system and adaptation of security policies, thereby enhancing the overall level of protection. The methodology entails the deployment of advanced tools and software, including Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), fuzzy testing, User and Entity Behavior Analytics (UEBA), User Activity Monitoring (UAM), Software Bill of Materials (SBOM), and machine learning techniques. Integral to the methodology are relevant libraries and databases such as the CIS Benchmark, Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs), Common Platform Enumeration (CPE) Dictionary, and Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS). These components ensure the standardization and integration of the methodology with other approaches and methods for the control and monitoring of information systems. In this article, the example of calculation of vulnerability estimation for model Object-Subject was considered.

The team of authors has developed a methodology for building access control systems based on fuzzy mathematics. The grounds of the approach are outlined in the work [1]. The methodology involves a combination of modern tools and methods of data analysis and information system states in order to determine the risk level of the access control system. The influence of factors in the "subject-object" system, caused by various aspects, including incorrect actions of the user, is considered. The methodology is based on FUZZY mathematics with the following implementation in the MATLAB package [2]. The presented material is an approbation of the previously developed methodology. It

considers the "subject-object" model of a particular information system, which reflects the structure of relationships between the indicators of the access control testing system to this information system (Fig. 1). We will assume that the subject is an entity that interacts with the system and is endowed with certain rights to perform actions with system objects, for example, a system user or a process. The entity is characterized by the degree of trust in its qualifications and actions in the system. An object is an entity (often a resource) represented by elements of the information system, which also have their own attributes. Software, file system, service, and equipment are considered as objects.

All subjects are characterized by the ability to interact with objects (change, add, update, etc.). The access control policy defines the possibility of the subject's influence on the object, described by the Access Control List (ACL) indicator.

The output parameter is the Access control system risk level, assessed on a scale of 0 to 1. This indicator is calculated using fuzzy derivation and mathematical calculations, using the values of the parameters characterizing both the Object and the Subject.

We will describe the "subject-object" interaction using model (1). Using the Algebra of Statements, we will describe the events according to the state of the indicators, which is presented in Fig. 1.

$$\begin{aligned} AL &= PRM \wedge PR \vee NT \wedge AV \vee AC \wedge AML \vee AR \wedge AML \vee EM, \\ OVL &= VC \wedge ISL \vee (VA \wedge OAF \vee VA) \vee LOI, \\ ACSR &= AL \wedge OVL, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where a possible event for the Subject indicator group will be presented as

$$AML = PML \vee SCA.$$

$$PML = RAL \wedge mPA \wedge ALD \wedge MPA \wedge EPH \wedge ALT \wedge MPL \wedge PCR \wedge SPE,$$

where the entered indicators are described in the standard [3].

Let's introduce linguistic variables for indicators of both Object and Subject corresponding to model (1). The input data of the production system of fuzzy output are the facts of certain states of the system, obtained at certain discrete moments, and dynamic, taking into account the results of constant monitoring of anomalies in the system, which are provided by modern tools and software, such as intrusion detection systems (IDS), fuzzy testing, User and Entity Behavior Analytics (UEBA), User Activity Monitoring (UAM), SBOM. Fuzzification of input data considers the predefined permission level access control list. The knowledge base is formed taking into account standardized

The output linguistic variable of the production system is the ACSRL risk level, the terms and functions of which are defined in the table. 1, according to [4].

Table 1. Linguistic variables Access control system risk level (ACSRL)

Терми ACSRL	Функція приналежності термів
Very high (VH)	$s(0,70\ 0,90)$
High (H)	$P_i(0,50\ 0,65\ 0,82\ 0,90)$
Substantial (S)	$P_i(0,30\ 0,42\ 0,58\ 0,70)$
Possible (P)	$P_i(0,10\ 0,18\ 0,35\ 0,50)$
Slight (S)	$s(0,10\ 0,30)$

The fuzzy inference production system has a hierarchical structure corresponding to model (1). Fig. 2 b)-i) presents some response surfaces of this hierarchical structure, and Fig. 2 a) presents the ACSRL response surface.

Fig.2 – Surface of fuzzy output a) ACSRL depend on AL & AS, b) VC&ISL, c) OAF&VIA, d) NTA &AV, e) AML&AR, i) AML&AC.

This is an example of system operation for a vector of input data under the conditions of operation of a real "subject-object" system using the built-in programming language of the Matlab package. The subject is the user, described by binary characteristics, and the object is some device characterized by phased data.

```
Subjects(1)=struct("RAL", 1,"mPA", 1,"ALD", 1,"MPA", 1,"EPH",
, 1,"ALT", 1,"MPL", 1,"PCR", 1,"SPE", 1);
```

```
Objects(2)=
struct("Name", "Switch", "OVL", "High", "OAF", "Constantly", "ISL", "
High", "LOD", "Low", "LOI", "High", "OVLP", [OVLP(2)]).
```

The vulnerability characteristic of the object looks like this:

```
OVLP(2)=
struct ("CVE", "CVE-2020-
35221", "VALUE", 8.8, "EM", "Not-
Defined", "AV", "Adjacent", "AC", "Low", "PR", "None", "UI", "None", "
VC", "High", "VA", "High", "VI", "High", "AR", "None").
```

Characteristics of the system as a whole:

```
NT=struct("NTA", "CAN", "NTS", "Open", "SPI", "Average").
```

The result of the system is a risk assessment ACSRL=0.64922.

Conclusions. The real example shows the operation of the developed system, which allows you to test the object of the system against the unauthorized influence of some subject and determine the assessment of the vulnerability of the "subject-object" connection.

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References

1. S. Parkinson, S. Khana, Identifying high-risk over-entitlement in access control policies using fuzzy logic, *Cybersecurity* 5:6 (2022) 1-17. [doi:10.1186/s42400-022-00112-1](https://doi.org/10.1186/s42400-022-00112-1).
2. MathWorks, 2024. URL: <https://www.mathworks.com/products/matlab.html>.
3. Common Vulnerability Scoring System version 4.0. User Guide. FIRST, 2023. URL: <https://www.first.org/cvss/>.
4. [International standard. Risk management, Risk assessment techniques, IEC 31010, Edition 2.0, 2019.](#)

BEAUTIFUL GRAPHS FROM SIMPLE GROUPS

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The commuting graph of a group

Let G be a finite group. The commuting graph of G is the graph with vertex set G , in which x and y are joined if $xy = yx$.

Here are the commuting graphs of the two non-abelian groups of order 8:

$$D_8 = \langle a, b : a^4 = 1, b^2 = 1, b^{-1}ab = a^{-1} \rangle \text{ and}$$

$$Q_8 = \langle a, b : a^4 = 1, b^2 = a^2, b^{-1}ab = a^{-1} \rangle.$$

